

Table 1. General combining ability effects* of parents for grain yield and other characters. Chainat, Thailand, 1992 WS.

Parent	Grain yield	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height	Tillers/hill	100-grain wt	Spikelets/panicle	% unfilled grain	Panicle length
<i>A lines</i>								
CNTA-1	14.43	2.40**	1.26*	0.34	-0.02*	4.60	2.52*	0.02
CNTA-7	3.82	0.50*	0.99	-0.19	-0.03**	10.71**	1.44	-0.03
CNTA-10	16.28	1.85**	3.51**	-0.16	-0.01	9.65**	0.66	0.22
CNTA-34	-34.53*	-4.82**	-5.76**	0.01	0.06**	-24.95**	-4.62**	-0.2
SE	13.89	0.25	0.72	0.31	0.01	2.54	1.00	0.14
<i>R lines</i>								
CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1	28.03	1.32**	-8.74**	1.04**	0.02**	-10.60**	-1.02	-1.47**
RD7	-127.49**	1.74**	1.95*	-1.35**	0.05**	-5.15	7.65**	0.45**
C4-63	-37.93*	-1.76**	-4.97**	-0.08	-0.10**	7.65**	5.61**	-0.85**
SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1	52.53**	-0.43	3.13**	-0.45	0.03**	4.65	-7.44**	0.78**
SPRLR75055-352-2-1	89.84**	-0.87**	8.63**	0.85*	0.01	3.46	-4.79**	1.09**
SE	15.53	0.28	0.81	0.34	0.01	2.84	1.12	0.15

*, ** = significant at the 5 and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 2. Heterosis (Ht), heterobeltiosis (Hb), and standard heterosis (Sh) in yield of the top 5 F₁ hybrids at Chainat, Thailand, 1991 WS.

F ₁ hybrid	Grain yield ^a (g/1.19 m ²)	Grain yield (%)			
		Ht	Hb	Sh	
				over RD23	over SPR60
CNTA-10/CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1	570.5 abcde	44.5	23.7	32.4	28.4
CNTA-10/SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1	654.0 a	43.9	41.8	51.7	47.2
CNTA-1/CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1	577.3 abcd	43.8	21.0	33.9	29.9
CNTA-7/SPRLR75055-352-2-1	641.8 ab	42.5	34.6	48.9	44.4
CNTA-34/CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1	517.3 cdefg	41.6	28.6	20.0	16.4
CNTA-1	477	defghi			
CNTA-7	476.8	defghi			
CNTA-10	461.3	fghijk			
CNTA-34	402.3	hijkl			
CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1	328.3	i			
RD7	371.8	jkl			
C4-63	366.5	jkl			
SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1	447.8	fghijk			
SPRLR75055-352-2-1	423.8	ghijkl			
RD23	431.0	ghijk			
SPR60	444.3	fghijk			
CV = 12.4 %					

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

SPR60) were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications in 1992 wet season (WS). Each treatment (plot) was one row of 21 plants, one plant per hill, with 25 × 25-cm spacing. Five plants from each plot were randomly measured for yield component analysis and 19 plants from 1.19 m² for yield analysis.

For the A lines, CNTA-10 and CNTA-1 were good general combiners

for yield, plant height, and panicle length (Table 1). CNTA-1 had the best GCA effect for tillers/hill, CNTA-7 for spikelets/panicle, and CNTA-34 for early days to 50% flowering, 100-grain weight, and low % unfilled grain.

For the R lines, SPRLR75055-352-2-1 and SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1 were good general combiners for yield, plant height, low % unfilled grain, and panicle length (Table 1).

C4-63 had the best GCA effect for early days to 50% flowering and spikelets/panicle, RD7 for 100-grain weight, and CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1 for tillers/hill.

The F₁ cross of CNTA-10/CNTRLR80140-14-1-1-1 had the highest heterosis in yield at 44.5% (Table 2). CNTA-10/SPRLR77034-PSL-17-1-1-1 had the highest heterobeltiosis at 41.8% and standard heterosis at 51.7% more than RD23 and 47.2% more than SPR60. ■

Isolation-free system for producing experimental hybrid rice seed for preliminary evaluation

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Artificial hybridization is impractical when hundreds of hybrid combinations requiring thousands of seeds must be produced for yield testing each season. We developed an isolation-free system for producing experimental hybrid rice seed for evaluation in preliminary yield trials.

In the system, various restorer (R) lines are grown side-by-side in 5 × 3-m plots (see figure). On the four sides of each plot, four rows of R plants are planted at 20 × 20-cm spacing to form a border to provide some isolation from adjoining plots. In the center of each plot are four 40-cm-wide vacant spaces, interspersed by single rows of R plants. The spaces can accommodate

up to 68 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) (A) plants at flowering (see figure).

A lines of experimental hybrids are planted five times at an 8-10 d interval. This staggered planting ensures a continuous supply of flowering A plants to synchronize with the flowering of R lines in different seed production plots. A lines are planted upwind from R lines and near the seed production plots to facilitate the transport of plants.

When primary tillers of A and R lines are at booting, their flag leaves are clipped. The two outermost border rows in the R plots are not clipped to demarcate the plots and to act as a barrier to pollen from adjoining plots. Three to five d after clipping, A plants are uprooted and relocated to the vacant spaces. Uprooting is done between 0630 h and 0800 h to reduce shock. A line plants are not used if more than 20% of their spikelets have already bloomed.

Pollen dispersal is increased at peak anthesis (1030 h to 1100 h) by shaking R line panicles with a bamboo stick. Pollen

Layout for isolation-free system for producing experimental rice hybrid seed.

movement to the adjoining plots is minimized by disturbing only R plants immediately surrounding the A plants. Supplementary pollination is done for 5-7 d or until pollen of a R line is exhausted. R line plants from seed production plots are harvested first, followed by A plants bearing the (A × R) F₁ seeds.

Two CMS lines yielded 4-5 g hybrid seed/plant during wet season and 7-10 g seed/plant during dry season using this system. Five to ten plants of a CMS line can produce 40 g of experimental hybrid seed for evaluation in an observation yield trial for two seasons. Twenty to 40 plants can produce 150 g experimental hybrid seed for evaluation in a replicated preliminary yield trial for two seasons.

We have been using the isolation-free seed production system at IRRRI for the past three seasons. During 1992, we produced seeds of 103 experimental hybrids for evaluation in preliminary yield trials. Seed contamination was 0-8%, with a mean of 1.7%.

We strongly recommend that hybrid rice breeders in national programs use this system for producing experimental hybrid rice seed for evaluation in preliminary yield trials. ■

Identifying maintainer and restorer lines for hybrid rice in Himachal Pradesh (HP), India

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Identifying maintainer and restorer lines in traditional varieties (TVs) and modern varieties (MVs) adapted to the agroclimatic conditions of HP is a prerequisite to initiating a hybrid rice program in the state. Cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line V20 A, which possesses wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm, seems ideally suited for this purpose.

Identified maintainer and restorer lines^a of V20 A at HPKV, Palampur, HP, India, 1991 wet season.

Cultivar	Based on	
	Pollen fertility	Spikelet fertility
Himadhan	M	M
R575	M	M
Kaladhan	M	M
CH1039	M	M
IR18482-Plp3-2-5-2	M	M
HPU2202	M	M
Debal	M	M
HPU5101	M	M
CH988	M	M
K39	PR	PR
Himalaya 741	-	PR
HPU799	-	PR
HPU2216	-	PR
IR9129-263-3-3-2-3-2	-	PR
HPU5039-Plp13-4-4-6-3B	PR	PR

^aM = effective maintainer (0% fertility), PR = partial restorer (10-69% pollen fertility and 10-79% spikelet fertility).